

PROBLEMS IN WORD LEARNING FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDENTS AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: English proficiency is determined by the vocabulary of foreign language learners as well as native speakers. While expanding one's vocabulary is important, it also presents various challenges, especially for non-native English students. Students with low vocabulary do not achieve satisfactory academic results in several university-level courses related to language skills, linguistics, literature, and translation. This article specifically aims to explore the problems encountered in learning English and suggests some vocabulary learning strategies to minimize potential problems.

Keywords: English Language Arts, Vocabulary Knowledge, Vocabulary Learning Challenges, Vocabulary Learning strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Thinking about language learning requires discussing vocabulary. This means that language cannot be separated from its vocabulary, because vocabulary is the foundation of language. As a result, knowing the vocabulary is the language is the most important component of learning. Hatch and Brown agree with this statement (1995: 1). They say that "vocabulary is the foundation for creating languages, and it plays a key role in communication." Today, English is spoken almost everywhere in the world, either as a first language, as a second language, or as a foreign language. In Uzbekistan, English is a foreign language, which includes both language ability and linguistic features. Language skills include listening, speaking, reading and writing, language aspects include pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, structure and fluency.

Teaching vocabulary is one of the most important aspects of any language classroom because it allows second language learners to understand and express themselves. By studying vocabulary, students can express themselves in English in writing and speaking. Students are encouraged to memorize terms while learning vocabulary. Also, whether they are nouns, verbs, adjectives, or adverbs, each they must understand the part of speech of the word. Students need to understand the meaning of terms when learning a foreign language. If students do not understand the meaning of the word, many consequences or effects can occur, for example, students will misinterpret the meaning of the message, and students will not want to learn English.

The most important aspect of learning a mother tongue or any other language is vocabulary. Learning a language cannot be done without studying its lexicon, which is

subject to infinite changes in meaning due to various contextual conditions. Along with phonetics/pronunciation and grammar, vocabulary is one of the most important aspects of learning a foreign language. In addition, vocabulary serves as a foundation for language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It is difficult to reach any level of the language without mastering the vocabulary. Vocabulary is the foundation of learning a second language. Nunan (1991) states that the development of sufficient vocabulary is essential for successful second language use because we have a large vocabulary gap to communicate clearly, the structures we learn and we cannot use functions. (McCarthy, 1990, p.viii) states that "no matter how well a student learns grammar, no matter how successfully mastering the sounds of a second language, cannot communicate in a second language without words that express broader meanings. occurs in any meaningful way." As Schmitt (2000) noted, "lexical knowledge is communicative competence and is central to second language acquisition." Communication in a second language allows you to express a wider range of meanings. In addition, vocabulary knowledge. creates serious difficulties that hinder their ability to acquire English. Many people believe that vocabulary is important in teaching and learning a second language because lexical knowledge is necessary for effective communication. Human. Language is defined by the vocabulary acquired or used, which students without vocabulary tend to use as a result learn the language.

The term vocabulary has different meanings suggested by teachers. For some, this represents sight word vocabulary as the immediate recognition of words by students. Others describe it as a vocabulary that represents words that students understand; also considered as listening-vocabulary or students' understanding of heard and spoken words. Content teachers describe it as content-specific words or academic vocabulary that reflects students' reduced oral and written vocabulary (Antonacci & O'Callaghan, 2011). Another definition of vocabulary provided by Hiebert and Kamil (2005) is the knowledge that students have about the meanings of words. They pointed out that there are two kinds of words: oral and written, and there are at least two types of knowledge: receptive (understanding or recognition) and productive (writing or speaking). Oral vocabulary is a set of terms that students understand when spoken or read aloud. Print vocabulary consists of terms that students understand while writing or reading aloud. According to Hiebert and Kamil, productive vocabulary is a group of terms that students are familiar with and use regularly when speaking or writing.

Language learners can expand their vocabulary, increase their vocabulary and develop their linguistic repertoire. However, vocabulary development is especially difficult for non-native English speakers who struggle with new word definitions,

spelling, pronunciation, correct word usage, inferring meaning from context, etc. There can be several reasons for such difficulties. For example, some studies in Uzbekistan have highlighted ineffective methods of teaching and learning English. Most teachers use students' mother tongue more than the target language to deliver lessons, which leads to poor student performance. Some other studies have also shown problems in vocabulary learning by students.

Vocabulary learning involves four stages: differentiation, understanding of meaning, recall, and consolidation and expansion of meanings. First, the discrimination stage involves distinguishing between sounds and letters. It helps with speaking, listening, reading and writing as students pronounce words correctly by distinguishing sounds and understand them when they read or hear them. Second, understanding meaning involves understanding the meaning of words by relating them to referents. Third, the remembering stage consists of the ability to retain meanings. Fourth, the consolidation and extension phase refers to the learning of new vocabulary and its integration into the students' vocabulary system (Grauberg, 1997). However, learning vocabulary usually puts a heavy burden on students. In other words, languages are productive and they constantly creates new words and adds to the vocabulary. Oxford (1990) points out that no rules are usually followed in learning the vocabulary used in learning grammar. Students typically encounter hundreds of words to learn and practice during their studies. It is believed that the weak linguistic performance of Uzbek students in English is mainly a sign of their low vocabulary. The researcher points out two serious facts that cause poor acquisition of vocabulary and lack of vocabulary of Uzbek students studying in general education schools. Participants included thirty-five students of various educational levels and nine male Uzbek teachers of English as a foreign language (EFL) in middle and high schools. Data were collected through a questionnaire and high school textbooks. The results show that students used poor vocabulary tactics such as relying only on a bilingual dictionary, asking others for definitions, etc. Similarly, the results indicate a deficit in the processing of vocabulary items and the presentation of all components of vocabulary knowledge. In the study, it is strongly recommended to teach the language step by step. This is often seen as a problem faced by students in learning English vocabulary. This qualitative study, using interviews and questionnaires, identifies various barriers to students' vocabulary learning.

In this study, the pronunciation and spelling of words (written and spoken forms do not always match), the selection of appropriate meanings of words (complexity of vocabulary knowledge), inflections of word forms (insufficient understanding of

grammar) and issues such as word overload are discussed. students are expected to learn. It is also a dictionary reveals some important variables of acquisition difficulties and assigns learning difficulties to different levels of language. For example, pronunciation problems refer to the sound system of the English language, inflection and word forms to the morphological system, word combinations, for example, to compounds and phrases, semantics, word groups to syntax, etc. . Another point is that learning vocabulary is an important element of learning a foreign language, focusing on the meanings of new terms. This study emphasizes basic vocabulary research and provides insight into teaching methods used by teachers in teaching vocabulary.

Research has shown that when words are presented in context and simple explanations are provided, understanding of these words increases (Biemiller & Boote, 2006) and word meanings are better learned (Stahl & Fairbanks, 1986). If an unfamiliar word can disrupt comprehension, the best time to introduce the meaning of the word may be when the word is encountered in the text.

Using Context Clues According to Nagy and Scott (2000), students use contextual analysis to determine the meaning of a word by carefully examining the surrounding text. Because students encounter such a large number of words as they read, some researchers believe that even small improvements in the ability to use contextual cues can lead to significant, long-term growth in vocabulary (Nagy, Herman, & Anderson, 1985 ; Nagy, Anderson, & Herman, 1987; Swanborn & de Glopper, 1999).

In short, the lexical resources of second and foreign language learners, as well as native speakers, are used to determine English proficiency. Increase vocabulary Although it is very important, it can be difficult, but learning from mistakes through different strategies at the same time plays an important role in the long way of gradual development.

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